

Towards Naturalistic Gentle Touch with a Soft Robotic Palm Interface

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Abstract. Replicating gentle, naturalistic stroking in a controlled manner remains challenging. We present a soft robotic palm capable of delivering strokes with precise velocity, force and temperature. In a pilot study ($N = 1$), pleasantness and sN400 amplitudes peaked at CT-optimal velocities, demonstrating the system’s potential for controlled touch research.

Keywords: Affective Touch, Soft robotics, Human touch simulation, EEG

1 Introduction

Gentle stroking touch promotes overall well-being and is associated with special mechanoreceptors called C-tactile afferents (CTs), which encodes its affective value. Yet, replicating such touch under controlled conditions remains challenging as existing stimulation methods differ substantially from natural human touch. To address these, we introduce a soft robotic palm interface capable of delivering naturalistic human stroking with precise control over velocity, force and temperature.

2 Methods

2.1 Hardware Design for Naturalistic Human Touch

Actuation and Sensing Integration. A two-axis linear rail system controls large horizontal and vertical motions. Load cells regulate contact force via cable tension. A 3D camera captures forearm geometry for modeling and control. A heating element provides skin-like temperatures, while an embedded sensor ensures thermal consistency.

The Touch Effector (Soft Palm) Design. The soft palm, 3D-printed from elastic TPU-95, has a pre-bent, shell-like geometry with actuation cables that deform the palm to wrap around the forearm, mimicking human touch [1]. To improve tactile realism, an inner layer of paper—chosen for its closest perceived similarity to skin—was added, compensating for TPU-95’s surface differences.

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Support Mechanisms for Arm Conformation. To compensate for the forearm’s non-uniform geometry, we designed an adjustable arm holder to elevate the wrist and flatten the contact region. We accommodated variations in arm size and curvature with four palm sizes for broader population coverage.

Fig. 1. Soft robotic palm interface (A), adjustable arm holder (B) and developed palm sizes variations (C). (D) Workplace generation (left) and the contact calibration process (right).

2.2 Software Framework for Naturalistic Human Touch

Soft Palm Modelling and Workplace Generation. A finite element model is used to model deformation of the soft robotic palm [2]. The palm is discretized into tetrahedral meshes with actuation cables modeled as massless elements exerting unilateral tensile forces. As the system is length controlled, a hybrid time-integration algorithm maps cable lengths to palm configurations. Contact vertices define forearm contact points and their deformations and respective cable length form the pre-generated workspace.

Human Arm Geometry Acquisition and Processing. The arm region is segmented from point cloud data from the 3D camera and key geometric features is extracted to determine the optimal arm holder angle and the most suitable soft robotic palm.

Static Touch Contact Calibration. We used a calibration-interpolation approach to determine control inputs for optimized contact at discrete forearm positions. An iterative closest point algorithm matches scanned arm geometry to pre-generated workspace and provides initial cable lengths (u_{fit}) and tensions (f_{fit}). These are fine-tuned to compensate for errors (e). A proportional controller adjusts cable tensions towards a predefined reference (f_r) to ensure gentle contact. The final control inputs (cable lengths, u_f , and vertical rail position, h_f) are used for stroke generation via linear interpolation.

2.3 System Validation

We validated the system with a previous protocol [3]. The participant’s left forearm was stroked at varying velocities while EEG was recorded (Fig. 2A). Palm-to-forearm contact was detected via copper strips connected to an Arduino Mega, which sent triggers to the EEG system. EEG data were filtered (0.1-30 Hz), re-referenced to average,

epoched (-1 to 1 s), cleaned via visual inspection and ICA, baseline-corrected (-0.2 to 0 s) and transformed via current source density. The sN400 component was analysed at contralateral somatosensory electrodes (Cz, C2, and C4) from 0.3 to 0.5 s post-touch.

3 Results and Discussion

Mean pleasantness ratings appeared to be highest at 1 and 3 cm/s (Fig. 2B). This trend was partially reflected in the sN400 with greater negativity at 3 cm/s (Fig. 2D). These preliminary findings broadly align with prior work.

Fig. 2. (A) Experimental trial paradigm. (B) Pleasantness ratings. (C) Event-related potentials (ERPs) time-locked to touch onset. (D) Mean sN400 amplitudes with 95% CI error bars.

4 Future Directions, Open Research Question and Interdisciplinary Exchange

Our soft robotic palm shows promise in delivering naturalistic, controlled touch. Future work will examine how temperature modulates perceived pleasantness at behavioral and neural level. Since paper only approximates certain human skin properties, we seek collaborations with material scientists to develop advanced skin-like materials that integrate force and temperature sensing, enabling more precise touch modulation and characterization.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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